

Level of health literacy of Leisure Time Monitors and its relationship with health variables

Iago Portela-Pino (✉ iagoportt92@gmail.com)

Isabel I University

Millan Brea-Castro

University of Vigo

Clara Portela-Pino

Galicia Sur Research Institute (IIS Galicia Sur), SERGAS-UVIGO

Margarita Pino-Juste

University of Vigo

Research Article

Keywords: Health Literacy, Leisure Time, Monitors, Health Variables

Posted Date: May 16th, 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2041390/v1>

License: © ⓘ This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

[Read Full License](#)

Abstract

Background: health literacy focused mainly on health care services and, to a very limited extent, on the ability to manage medical information. Low health literacy has been linked to decreased adherence to treatment, poor disease awareness, poor self-care management and poor treatment outcomes. The aim of this study is to acquire representative data on the health literacy of leisure time instructors.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational design was used with a purposive sample of leisure time monitors from the Autonomous Community of Galicia. The instrument consists of two parts. The first part asks about the variables related to self-perception of health status and the second part, the HL was measured using the HLS-EU-Q47 scale.

Results: Among the results, it stands out that, in spite of the youth of the leisure time educators, almost all of them report having had some health problem and only 3% have a high level of HL.

There are almost no differences between the health variables with respect to the level of HL. However, the tendency is that the lower the HA, the higher the number of visits and admissions and the lower the self-perception of health, although it is necessary to expand the sample of educators who regularly visit the health services.

Conclusión: The importance of accessing health information and understanding risk factors to identify the causes of a disease and make decisions is highlighted. The low level of HL of the monitors makes it difficult to implement and evaluate interventions in the non-formal educational environment. It will be important to determine lines of action for their training.

Introduction

Originally, health literacy focused mainly on health care services and, to a very limited extent, on the ability to manage medical information. Over the years the meaning has gradually expanded to include more complex and interconnected skills such as reading and acting on information, communicating needs to professionals and understanding instructions given by professionals. Currently, the term continues to expand and involves information seeking, decision making, problem solving, critical thinking and communication skills, as well as social, personal and cognitive skills [1].

Low health literacy has been linked to decreased adherence to treatment, poor disease awareness, poor self-care management and poor treatment outcomes. There are now a growing number of studies attesting to the fact that people with health literacy problems are also less likely to participate in health promotion programs or use preventive services [2, 3]. Available evidence shows that more people than is usually believed have limited health literacy [2]. In fact, different studies indicate that the population has a very poor level of health literacy, although the percentage varies across countries and in different population groups [4–7].

Health literacy is the degree to which individuals can obtain, process, and understand the basic health information and services they need to make informed and appropriate health decisions. This ability includes the ability to interpret documents, read and write prose, use quantitative information, and speak and listen effectively in a health care setting and use the information to make appropriate health decisions and follow treatment instructions (Muhanga, and Malungo, 2017).

Although leisure activities have a fundamental mission for good physical and psychological health of the young generation, very little research has focused on the health literacy of educators, both informal and non-formal settings. The amount of leisure time is critical for people's psychosocial functioning and health [9] and also for their subjective [10, 11] and emotional well-being [12]. Indeed, Weybright et al. (2019) highlight that leisure experiences make important contributions to individual and community health as they promote health and reduce negative outcomes at the individual and community level as it aids in disease prevention by reducing their risk [14].

Leisure-time educational settings are appropriate venues for health literacy training [15, 16] as community-based health literacy interventions offer great potential to improve health knowledge, skills, and behaviors and, consequently, better community health outcomes [17]. However, health literacy assessment predominantly focuses on literacy and communication skills of individuals in clinical settings. In the educational setting, there are hardly any studies, despite the fact that educators have an important role in health promotion (Cheng and Wong, 2015; Ahmadi and Montazeri, 2019; Lamanauskas, 2019). Along these lines, there has been research on the health benefits of recreational activities, reflecting the role of leisure in public health; but yet there is hardly any research on the role of leisure as a prevention tool [13, 20].

The importance of this study is based on the hypothesis that a low level of health literacy of leisure time monitors may hinder the implementation and evaluation of interventions in the non-formal educational environment. However, there is an increasing demand for these professionals given the increase in demand for structured and guided leisure activities. In fact, local and state administrations, as well as companies have incorporated leisure time programs into their training offer.

In fact, health promotion understands leisure as a tool through which disease risks can be minimized given the biopsychosocial benefits of leisure from a salutogenic health perspective [21].

Therefore, the aim of this study is to describe the health profile of educators and to establish their level of health literacy and relationships with health variables in order to establish lines of formative action.

Method

A cross-sectional observational design was used with a purposive sample of leisure time monitors from the Autonomous Community of Galicia in order to determine their mastery of the different capacities and dimensions of HL, as well as to establish the association with health variables.

Participants

The study participants are 156 women and 26 men with a mean age of 28.65 (Min. =19; Max. =50).

Instrument

The instrument consists of two parts. The first part asks about the variables related to health: visits to the emergency department, hospital admissions, physical exercise, who accompanies the patient to the doctor, and self-perception of health status. In the second part, the HL was measured using the HLS-EU-Q47 scale. This self-perception scale consists of 47 questions that allow inquiring about three different dimensions: Health treatment and care (ability to access, understand, evaluate and make decisions about medical information), Disease prevention (ability to access, understand, evaluate and make decisions about risk factors), Health promotion (ability to access, understand, evaluate and make decisions about health-related information and understand its meaning). Each of these dimensions has four HA capabilities: Access (ability to access information on medical or clinical issues, risk factors and get up to date), Understand (ability to understand medical information, on risk factors health-related information and understand the meaning), Evaluate (ability to interpret and evaluate medical information, on risk factors and information related to health issues), Apply (ability to make informed decisions on medical problems, risk factors and thoughtful opinion on health issues). Each item asks about the degree of difficulty encountered by each participant in performing a particular task on a Likert scale with 4 categories from 1 to 4.

The reliability of the scale and of all its capabilities and dimensions ranges from 0.786 to 0.947 for the HL scale.

Procedure

The monitors completed the instrument sent by e-mail to their e-mail addresses during the month of October 2020 when we were already immersed in the midst of the pandemic derived from COVID-19. Their participation was voluntary and anonymous and their informed consent was requested respecting all ethical procedures for data collection, following the deontological standards recognized by the Declaration of Helsinki (revision of Fortaleza, Brazil, 2013) and in accordance with the recommendations of Good Clinical Practice of the EEC (document 111/3976/88 of July 1990) and the current Spanish legal regulations governing research.

Data analysis

First, the mean, standard deviation and minimum and maximum values of the capacities, dimensions and subdimensions that make up the health literacy scale were calculated. To verify the parametric assumption of normality, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used ($p > 0.05$). Statistical analyses were performed with the SPSS v. 23 statistical program (IBM Corp., 2012). The significance level for all analyses was $p < 0.05$.

Results

1. Health profile of the recreational instructor

The 28.6% of the leisure time monitors in Galicia have a poor HL, i.e. below a score of 25.88. Only 3.3% have a high level of HL; i.e. above a score of 41.45. 96.8% have never had any health problems.

Almost 50% of the participants in the study have never visited the emergency department and the other 50% have been to the emergency department. And 48.9% have been admitted to a hospital at least once and 11% more than three times. Ninety percent have someone to accompany them to the doctor.

The practice of physical exercise is occasional (58.8%), 12.1% do not practice any type of exercise and 29.1% do it frequently.

They do not have a good perception of their health and consider it to be fair (62.1%) or poor (35.7%).

[Table 1]

Table 1
Descriptive of the health profile of the leisure time monitors.

	Independent variables	Frecuencia	Porcentaje
Grouped HL level	Deficient	52	28,6
	Average	124	68,1
	Excellent	6	3,3
Emergency department visits	None	90	49,5
	3 or less	83	45,6
	More than 3	9	4,9
Hospital admissions	None	89	48,9
	3 or less	73	40,1
	More than 3	20	11,0
Physical exercise	Never	22	12,1
	Occasionally	107	58,8
	Frequently	53	29,1
Medical accompaniment	No	18	9,9
	Yes	164	90,1
Self-perception of health status	Very bad	3	1,6
	Bad	65	35,7
	Regular	113	62,1
	Good	1	,5

2. Level of health literacy of the monitors in terms of skills and dimensions

The health literacy level of leisure time instructors is very low. (28,6 =). With respect to the HL capabilities, it ranges from understanding, which is the highest (30,84 =) and evaluating/processing is the lowest (25,72 =). In the case of the dimensions, the highest average is in the dimension of attention and care of the disease (30,43 =) and the lowest disease prevention (24,51 =).

[Table 2]

Table 2
Level of health literacy of leisure time instructors

	Access	Understand	Evaluate	Apply	Total
Health care and attention	33,10	31,94	22,50	34,24	30,43
Disease prevention	26,07	34,34	25,42	24,51	24,51
Health promotion	29,16	26,14	29,25	26,04	27,55
Total	29,42	30,84	25,72	28,26	28,6

3. Inferential análisis

If we analyze the level of HA in relation to different health variables, we can affirm that there are almost no differences between the different dimensions and capacities with respect to any of the health variables (visits to the emergency department, hospital admissions, physical exercise practice and self-perception of health status).

We have only found significant differences between the monitors who have used the emergency department and the number of hospital admissions, being, in both cases, lower the capacity to access information on treatment and health care (access care) in those who have used this service 3 times or less. The number who have attended more than three times is very small (n = 9).

With respect to the number of hospital admissions there are also differences in the ability to understand health-related risk factors which makes prevention difficult (prevention understand) and in the ability to access information on medical or clinical topics, risk factors and to update on these topics (access) being lower in the group of 3 times or less.

With respect to the practice of physical exercise, there are differences in the dimension of health promotion and the capacities of attention to process, prevention to process, promotion to understand and apply between the monitors who never do physical activity and those who do it frequently. This implies that monitors who have a lower rate of physical activity have greater problems in evaluating health information and its risk factors, but also in understanding and making decisions about health-related information and understanding its meaning.

[Table 3].

Table 3

A NOVA calculation for each dimension and capacity as a function of health-related polytomous variables.

	N	□	DS	F	Sig.	95% del IC para la media		Bonferroni
						Lower limit	Upper limit	
Use of emergency services								
ATTENTION access	None	90	30,70	6,621	3,663(.028)	29,3191	32,0929	1-2 = .023
	3 or less	83	29,81	5,46		28,6269	31,0116	2-3 = .017
	More than 3	9	33,44	5,16		29,4769	37,4213	
Hospital admissions								
ATTENTION access	None	89	34,12	8,72	3,852(.023)	32,2915	35,9669	1-2 = .015
	3 or less	73	31,16	7,15		29,4954	32,8334	2-3 = .012
	More than 3	20	35,62	7,70		32,0195	39,2305	
PREVENTION understand	None	89	35,51	10,071	3,244(.041)	33,3964	37,6398	1-2 = .037
	3 or less	73	32,26	8,10		30,3764	34,1594	2-3 = .042
	More than 3	20	36,66	8,53		32,6741	40,6592	
ACCESS	Never	22	23,34	8,87	7,12(.001)	19,4067	27,2789	0-2 = .001
	Occas.	106	27,00	7,71		25,5220	28,4953	1-2 = .029
	Freq.	53	30,40	7,24		28,4069	32,4029	
HEALTH PROMOTION	Physical Activity Index							
	Never	22	19,12	5,70	3,76(.025)	16,6010	21,6566	0-2 = .035

Leyenda: Ocass.= Occasionally; Frec.= Frequently

	N	□	DS	F	Sig.	95% del IC para la media		Bonferroni		
						Lower limit	Upper limit			
	Occas.	107	21,92	9,46			20,1101	23,7373		
	Freq.	53	25,07	9,78			22,3806	27,7766		
Care process	Never	22	21,36	6,05	4.34(.014)		18,6785	24,0488	0-2 = .017	
	Occas.	107	24,85	9,91			22,9587	26,7609		
	Freq.	53	28,23	10,41			25,3695	31,1085		
Prevention process	Never	22	23,29	9,50	3,56(.030)		19,0805	27,5104	0-2 = .045	
	Occas.	106	25,46	9,21			23,6899	27,2378		
	Freq.	53	28,69	8,19			26,4352	30,9547		
Promotion understand	Never	22	17,99	9,65	16,58(.000)		13,7114	22,2735	0-1 = .003	
	Occas.	107	25,22	9,20			23,4622	26,9896		0-2 = .000
	Freq.	53	31,05	9,12			28,5396	33,5673		
Promotion apply	Never	22	22,48	6,32	3,75(.025)		19,6809	25,2938	0-2 = .029	
	Occas.	107	25,31	8,35			23,7136	26,9175		
	Freq.	53	27,90	8,42			25,5828	30,2278		
	Never	22	25,39	4,75	4,86(.009)		23,2900	27,5097	0-2 = .012	
	Occas.	107	27,81	6,83			26,5079	29,1290		
	Freq.	53	30,37	7,07			28,4208	32,3234		
Leyenda: Ocass.= Occasionally; Frec.= Frequently										

If we use Spearman's correlation to establish the relationship between self-perception of health and the different dimensions and capabilities of health literacy, we find that these are positive, although very low, but this may be due to the low dispersion of the data, since the monitors are mainly grouped between a poor and fair perception of their health.

[Table 4].

Table 4
Correlations between self-perceived health and different dimensions and capabilities

Dimensiones y capacidades	r	Sig. (bilateral)
HEALTH CARE	,095	,203
DISEASE PREVENTION	,211**	,004
HEALTH PROMOTION	,275**	,000
ACCESS CARE	,019	,801
CARE understand	,092	,219
CARE process	,107	,153
CARE apply	,078	,297
PREVENTION access	,271**	,000
PREVENTION understand	,177*	,017
PREVENTION process	,138	,064
PREVENTION apply	,099	,183
PROMOTION access	,262**	,000
PROMOTION understand	,166*	,026
PROMOTION process	,170*	,022
PROMOTION apply	,271**	,000
ACCESS	,235**	,001
UNDERSTAND	,193**	,010
PROCESS	,164*	,028
APPLY	,208**	,005
HL	,232**	,002

We found that the higher the self-perception of health, the higher the dimension of disease prevention and health promotion, and the higher also all the capabilities except health care and the categories of prevention process and apply.

Discussion

Health literacy is an important factor for the health of the population, however, few studies have described the association between health characteristics and the level of health literacy in the population and, in monitors or educators, in particular.

Leisure monitors in Galicia have a low level of health literacy, especially in the ability to process medical information and in the dimension of disease prevention, which may influence the interpretation of health information, but also of the risk factors that could prevent it.

At a general level the population has low literacy. In the European comparative survey on health literacy in eight countries (Austria, Bulgaria, Germany, Greece, Ireland, the Netherlands, Poland, and Spain Sørensen et al. (2015a) note that 12% of respondents show insufficient health literacy and 47% had limited health literacy (insufficient or problematic), although these data differ between countries. In Germany more than half of adults have limited health literacy [3], in Ireland 14% [4], in Israel, 31% have inadequate or problematic health literacy [5] and in Iran the health literacy of the population is also inadequate [6] and in China, although there is great variation by region, the proportion of respondents with adequate health literacy was 22.3% on average [7].

We found very few studies on the level of HL in educators despite the fact that educators play a very important role as their health literacy directly influences the understanding of knowledge acquired by participants in leisure programs[23]. A study in Turkey showed adequate teacher health literacy in only 26.2% of study participants[24]. In Iran, Ahmadi and Montazeri (2019) found inadequate health literacy in 7.3% of the participants and problematic in 43.3%. In this regard, [23] indicate that educators lack knowledge and practical skills related to HA, however, they can play a key role as health promoters [19].

Low levels of individual health literacy, contribute to worse health outcomes due to late detection of the disease, lack of knowledge of the disease and its symptoms or worse doctor-patient communication or increased risk of suffering an adverse event [25], are related to less effective participation in activities related to self-care[26, 27], affect patient safety and access to care [28], and raise the cost of healthcare services [29].

Leisure time monitors in Galicia have a low self-perception of their health and, moreover, there are hardly any differences with respect to the level of HA if we take into account the different health variables. In fact, we can affirm that those who use the emergency department the most are less able to access health information (accessing care) and the number of hospital admissions ranges between 3 times or less.

With respect to the number of hospital admissions, there are also differences in the ability to access information and understand the risk factors of a disease, being lower in the group of 3 times or less.

These results highlight the importance of accessing health information and understanding risk factors to identify the causes of disease and make decisions. In fact, different studies have made clear the relationship between low health literacy and higher hospitalizations; higher use of emergency care; lower receipt of mammograms and vaccinations; lower ability to take medications appropriately; lower ability to

interpret health labels and messages; and, among older people, poorer overall health status and higher mortality rates [3, 5, 22, 26, 30, 31] .

With respect to physical activity, differences in literacy are established in those who do it frequently and those who never do it, especially in health promotion and care skills process, prevention process, promotion understand, promotion apply, process, and apply. Low health literacy is marginally but significantly associated with low physical activity[32, 33], poor adherence to physical activity guidelines [34] and HA can help support sustained participation in moderate to vigorous physical activity (MVPA) during aging [35].

We found that the higher the self-perceived health, the higher the dimension of disease prevention and health promotion and the higher all the less attention capabilities and the categories of prevention process and apply. Adequate HA is related to a good self-perceived health status and receiving health education on a frequent basis [7].

Conclusions

Health literacy not only determines people's motivation and competence levels to obtain and understand health-related information, but also reinforces self-care skills.

The poor health perception and low health literacy level of leisure time instructors may hinder the transmission of knowledge, processes and values to their learners; but also their self-care and communicative relationship with health care providers and the use of these services. Greater efforts will be needed to promote health literacy in this group, increase awareness of the need to acquire a good level of HA, facilitate the understanding of health-related information, and intensify research in this field.

The data are likely to have been influenced by the size of the different sample groups. However, the HL trend identified in the leisure time monitors will enable those responsible to address health literacy of educators-in-training.

In addition, it will be necessary to design, implement and evaluate different educational interventions that address HA in order to establish scientific evidence on their effectiveness.

Possible lines of action in the training of leisure time monitors

Taking into account the conclusions of this study, lines of action have been proposed to alleviate the deficiencies in the training of leisure time monitors in order to promote healthy lifestyles and take advantage of the communicative interaction generated in leisure activities. The aim is to achieve public health literacy understood as "the extent to which individuals and groups can obtain, process, understand, evaluate and act on the information needed to make public health decisions that benefit the community" [36].

1. Cognitive competencies

The most important cognitive skills in relation to health literacy focus on the processing of health-related information. That is, content that involves the use of memory, attention, perception, creativity and abstract thinking. Therefore, it is necessary to include content in training programs on health determinants, psycho-evolutionary characteristics of the human being, general knowledge on the most common pathologies and health problems, among others.

2. Emotional competencies

The leisure time educator must master strategies that allow educating participants in socio-educational programs to maintain harmonious relationships with other people and the natural and social environment. This implies mastering basic social skills, capacity for effective communication, active listening, respect, pro-social attitudes, assertiveness, etc. But also to reflect on the role of the leisure time educator as a health promoter

3. Methodological competencies

We refer to the ability to organize, structure and plan a methodological system and the application of appropriate procedures seeking solutions to the problems detected and establishing a transfer of experiences to new situations so that learning is functional.

In this section it will be important to master self-management techniques, design of physical and natural environments that favor healthy habits, active methodologies, management of digital applications for health, procedures and techniques for program evaluation, among others.

Declarations

Author Statements:

Competing interests

None

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The participation was voluntary and anonymous and their informed consent was requested respecting all ethical procedures for data collection, following the deontological standards recognized by the Declaration of Helsinki (revision of Fortaleza, Brazil, 2013) and in accordance with the recommendations of Good Clinical Practice of the EEC (document 111/3976/88 of July 1990) and the current Spanish legal regulations governing research.

In Spain, the authorisation and development of any research project on human beings or biological material will require the prior and perceptive favourable report of the Research Ethics Committee (REC) (*art. 2.e of the Biomedical Research Law 14/2007*). However, for observational studies where no personal data that may identify the interviewee are requested or these are computed in general, only

informed consent is necessary. Therefore, observational studies without drugs that do not involve interventions or the use of biological samples of human origin that only use clinical records or other anonymous or anonymised personal data do not require the authorisation of the CEIC.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable. The datasets used and/or analysed during the current study available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests

There is not Competing interests

Funding

Not applicable

Authors' contributions

Portela-Pino Iago and Brea Castro, Millán carried out the field study, the description of the results and the final correction. Clara Portela-Pino carried out the theoretical framework, the discussion, the design of the study and the final correction. Pino-Juste, Margarita designed the study, carried out the statistical analysis and the final correction.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable

References

1. Mancuso JM. Health literacy: A concept/dimensional analysis. *Nurs Health Sci.* 2008;10:248–55.
2. Van den Broucke S. Health literacy: a critical concept for public health. *Arch Public Heal.* 2014;72:10.
3. Schaeffer D, Berens E-M, Vogt D. Health Literacy in the German Population. *Dtsch Aerzteblatt Online.* 2017;114:53–60.
4. Sahm LJ, Wolf MS, Curtis LM, McCarthy S. Prevalence of Limited Health Literacy Among Irish Adults. *J Health Commun.* 2012;17:100–8.
5. Levin-Zamir D, Baron-Epel OB, Cohen V, Elhayany A. The Association of Health Literacy with Health Behavior, Socioeconomic Indicators, and Self-Assessed Health From a National Adult Survey in Israel. *J Health Commun.* 2016;21:61–8.

6. Dadipoor S, Ramezankhani A, Aghamolaei T, Rakhshani F, Safari-Moradabadi A. Evaluation of Health Literacy in the Iranian Population. *Heal Scope*. 2018;In Press In Press.
7. Li Z, Tian Y, Gong Z, Qian L. Health Literacy and Regional Heterogeneities in China: A Population-Based Study. *Front Public Heal*. 2021;9:1–9.
8. Muhanga, M. I. & Malungo JR. The what, why and how of health literacy: a systematic review of literature. 2017.
9. Synowiec-Piłat M, J drzejek M, Pał ga A, Zmysłona B. Work-life (im)balance? The amount of leisure of Wrocław adults in the context of health promotion. *Health Promot Int*. 2021;36:1084–94.
10. Kuykendall, L., Tay, L., & Ng V. Leisure engagement and subjective well-being: A meta-analysis. *Psychol Bull*. 2015;141:364.
11. Kuykendall L, Boemerman L, Zhu Z. *The Importance of Leisure for Subjective Well-Being*. 2018.
12. Chen ST, Hyun J, Graefe AR, Mowen AJ, Almeida DM, Sliwinski MJ. The Influence of Leisure Engagement on Daily Emotional Well-Being. <https://doi.org/101080/0149040020201757537>. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490400.2020.1757537>.
13. Weybright EH, Caldwell LL, Weaver RH. Preventing leisure from being overlooked: Intersecting leisure and prevention sciences. <https://doi.org/101080/0022221620191617646>. 2019;50:394–412.
14. Peel N, Maxwell H, McGrath R. Leisure and health: conjoined and contested concepts. <https://doi.org/101080/1174539820191682017>. 2019;24:295–309.
15. Cheng NYI, Wong MYE. Knowledge and Attitude of School Teachers towards Promoting Healthy Lifestyle to Students. *Health (Irvine Calif)*. 2015;7:119–26.
16. Mirzapour Ermaki R, Mirzaie M, Naghibi Sistani MM, Literacy H. Oral health literacy and health behavior of primary school teachers in Babol. *J Heal Lit*. 2019;3:66–74.
17. Guzys D, Kenny A, Dickson-Swift V, Threlkeld G. A critical review of population health literacy assessment. *BMC Public Health*. 2015;15:215.
18. Lamanauskas V & AD. Identifying Primary School Teachers' Health Literacy | *Journal of Turkish Science Education*. *J Turkish Sci Educ*. 2019;16:451–66.
19. Ahmadi F, Montazeri A. Health Literacy of Pre-Service Teachers from Farhangian University: A Cross-Sectional Survey. *Int J Sch Heal*. 2019;In Press In Press.
20. Fredriksson I, Geidne S, Eriksson C. Leisure-time youth centres as health-promoting settings: Experiences from multicultural neighbourhoods in Sweden. *Scand J Public Health*. 2018;46 20_suppl:72–9.
21. McGrath R, Maxwell H, Association NP-LS, 2019 U. Unravelling linkages between leisure and health discourses. *Leis Stud Assoc Conf*. 2019.
22. Sørensen K, Pelikan JM, Röthlin F, Ganahl K, Slonska Z, Doyle G, et al. Health literacy in Europe: comparative results of the European health literacy survey (HLS-EU). *Eur J Public Health*. 2015;25:1053–8.

23. Lamanauskas V, Augienė D. Identifying Primary School Teachers Health Literacy. *Turkish J Sci Educ.* 2019;16:451–66.
24. Yilmazel G, Çetinkaya F. Health literacy among schoolteachers in Corum, Turkey. *EMHJ-Eastern Mediterr Heal J.* 2015;21:598–605.
25. Pino-Juste M. Alfabetización en Salud: Educar para Mejorar los Resultados en Salud. In: *Intervención en Contextos Clínicos y de la Salud. Nuevas realidades.* Dykinson; 2020. p. 101–10.
26. Beauchamp A, Buchbinder R, Dodson S, Batterham RW, Elsworth GR, McPhee C, et al. Distribution of health literacy strengths and weaknesses across socio-demographic groups: a cross-sectional survey using the Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ). *BMC Public Health.* 2015;15:678.
27. Heijmans M, Uiters E, Rose T, Hofstede J, Devillé W, Heide I van der, et al. Study on sound evidence for a better understanding of health literacy in the European Union. 2014.
28. Hersh L, Salzman B, Snyderman D. Health literacy in primary care practice. *Am Fam Physician.* 2015;92:118–24.
29. Cho YI, Lee SYD, Arozullah AM, Crittenden KS. Effects of health literacy on health status and health service utilization amongst the elderly. *Soc Sci Med.* 2008;66:1809–16.
30. Berkman ND, Sheridan SL, Donahue KE, Halpern DJ, Crotty K. Low health literacy and health outcomes: an updated systematic review. *Ann Intern Med.* 2011;115:97–107.
31. Walters R, Leslie SJ, Polson R, Cusack T, Gorely T. Establishing the efficacy of interventions to improve health literacy and health behaviours: A systematic review. *BMC Public Health.* 2020;20:1–17.
32. Matsushita M, Harada K, Arao T. Relation between communicative and critical health literacy and physical activity in Japanese adults: a cross-sectional study. *J Phys Fit Sport Med.* 2018;7:75–80.
33. Garcia-Codina O, Juvinyà-Canal D, Amil-Bujan P, Bertran-Noguer C, González-Mestre MA, Masachs-Fatjo E, et al. Determinants of health literacy in the general population: results of the Catalan health survey. *BMC Public Health.* 2019;19:1122.
34. Geboers B, de Winter AF, Luten KA, Jansen CJM, Reijneveld SA. The Association of Health Literacy with Physical Activity and Nutritional Behavior in Older Adults, and Its Social Cognitive Mediators. *J Health Commun.* 2014;19:61–76.
35. Kobayashi LC, Wardle J, Wolf MS, von Wagner C. Health Literacy and Moderate to Vigorous Physical Activity During Aging, 2004–2013. *Am J Prev Med.* 2016;51:463–72.
36. Freedman DA, Bess KD, Tucker HA, Boyd DL, Tuchman AM, Wallston KA. Public Health Literacy Defined. *Am J Prev Med.* 2009;36:446–51.